

SYSTEMIC BARRIERS TO SUSTAINABLE RURAL ROAD INFRASTRUCTURE

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Abstract: This thesis is devoted to the scientific, theoretical and practical analysis of systemic factors that hinder the sustainable development of rural road infrastructure. Rural roads are an essential communicative foundation for territorial economic activity, the delivery of agricultural products to markets, access to education and health services, employment, and the development of local entrepreneurship. At the same time, their efficiency is determined not only by the volume of new construction or reconstruction, but also by such factors as financial sustainability, a culture of maintenance, institutional coordination, digital monitoring, climate resilience, and public oversight. In recent years, Uzbekistan has implemented important measures to modernize the road sector, promote the integrated development of regions, improve road safety, and rehabilitate rural roads in cooperation with international financial institutions. In particular, the Development Strategy, presidential decisions on improving the road sector, and international projects aimed at strengthening rural road resilience increase the relevance of this topic.

Keywords: rural roads, sustainable infrastructure, systemic barriers, transport policy, road assets, financing, maintenance, climate resilience, institutional governance, public oversight

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